

Continuity Equation as One Part of Work-Impulse Dichotomy in Quantum Mechanics

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Classical mechanics contains a well-known dichotomy, namely that of work: $\int F dx =$ change in KE and impulse, $\int F dt =$ change in p (momentum). The former view is concerned with time and velocity, while the latter is not as $p = m_1 v_1 = m_2 v_2$, i.e. the same impulse may occur for two different velocities. When solving classical mechanical problems, however, the time view (conservation of energy equation, Newton's second law) is utilized and the impulse picture, usually ignored.

We suggest that in quantum mechanics, one must retain both dichotomies as they are linked to each other as they are in classical physics. In fact, we argue that in quantum mechanics interactions are based on the impulse picture, which in some problems, such as one dimensional photon reflection-refraction, make it the only scenario which solves the problem. (Actually the impulse scenario makes use of flux values and so is intertwined with the time picture.)

In the literature (1) etc, the continuity equation: $d/dt \text{ partial density} = d/dx \{ \text{velocity}(x) \text{ density}(x,t) \}$ seems to be a common starting point for deriving the Schrodinger equation. We argue that this approach only considers the time-work-kinetic energy scenario a priori and ignores, a priori, the impulse approach to interactions. The impulse picture is a physical description of interactions and so both scenarios should be introduced together a priori. What is usually done is to consider only the time picture and then hypothesize on mathematical grounds that: $\text{density}(x,t) = W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ instead of considering the wavefunction form as the representation of the impulse picture which governs interactions. In fact, the time-independent Schrodinger equation is a combination of both scenarios. The work-kinetic energy picture must appear because $V(x)$ is used, but actual interactions occur via impulses and their unusual associated $\exp(ipx)$ probability.

Classical Mechanics and the Work, Impulse Dichotomy

Classical mechanics introduces the ideas of work and impulse i.e.

Change in KE (kinetic energy) = $\int F dx$ ((1a)) and Change in $p = \int F dt$ ((1b))

The integral in ((1a)) is called work and that in ((1b)) impulse. Traditionally in classical mechanics one focuses on a conservation of energy equation, or Newton's second law which is the differential equation equivalent. The impulse picture is overlooked as one is interested in changes in x in time, velocities, acceleration etc i.e. the dynamics of the problem. This viewpoint is carried over into fluid dynamics in which a dynamic continuity equation, which focuses on changes in time, is considered:

$$d/dt \text{ partial density} = d/dx \{ \text{velocity}(x) \text{ density}(x,t) \} \quad ((2))$$

The impulse picture does not focus on time because $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ create the same physical impulse i.e. the same damage to a target. The focus is more on the effect of a change in momentum, not in the system changing in time. Thus knowledge of Δp without knowing v does not tell one about a change in velocity.

We point out that both work and impulse appear in classical mechanics and are consistent. There seems, however, to be a preference in using the idea of work and not impulse, as conservation of energy or Newton's laws suffice to solve problems.

Quantum One Dimensional Reflection-Refraction of Light

In quantum mechanics, both the work and impulse pictures also occur and are consistent, but the focus seems to be on impulse as it describes the interaction. In fact, if one considers the one dimensional reflection-refraction of a photon beam at $x=0$ (with an $n_1=1$ n_2 barrier along the y axis) and writes the "time" picture in terms of fluxes one has:

$$AA/c = BB/c + CC/c2 \quad \text{where } c2=c/n2 \quad ((3))$$

Here AA , BB , and CC are the incident, reflected and refracted intensities. AA shows that flux is explicitly positive. $((3))$ represents the time picture (consistent with conservation of photon number or energy (if one multiplies by e), but it is one equation and there are two unknowns B, C if A is known. There is nothing wrong with $((3))$, but it is one part of the work-impulse dichotomy and does not solve the problem.

Given that work and impulse are consistent, one need not search for a second independent equation to $((3))$, but rather may break $((3))$ into independent equations using differences of squares:

$$A + B = C \quad ((4a)) \quad \text{and} \quad pA - pB = p2C \quad ((4b))$$

$((4a))$ and $((4b))$ are, we argue, the impulse picture which allows one to solve the problem.

Thus, unlike classical mechanics for which the work-kinetic energy, potential energy approach is enough to solve the problem and impulse may be ignored, such does not seem to be the case for quantum interactions. We suggest that this idea carries over into the quantum bound state.

Quantum Bound State

The quantum bound state utilizes the notion of potential energy, often taken directly from classical physics, and so the time, work, kinetic energy viewpoint is automatically used. In classical mechanics, this viewpoint would be sufficient, but it is not in quantum mechanics. Interactions occur according to the impulse approach which associates each free particle with momentum p with a two dimensional probability $\exp(ipx)$. We argue that one is forced to make use of the dichotomy of work, impulse in order to solve the quantum bound problem. The time-kinetic -energy picture requires a kinetic energy at x , but this in turn requires the measurement of p at x which cannot be performed decisively due to $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. the wavelength

habr/p. As a result, one is forced to use $\exp(ipx)$ for many p's as the unusual probability needed to calculate an average $pp/2m$ i.e.

$$KE(x) = \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ pp/2m \ \exp(ipx) \} / \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \} \quad ((5))$$

Then $KE(x)+V(x) = E_n$ ((6))

((6)) is equivalent to the Schrodinger equation and is obtained by combining both the time work kinetic energy picture and the impulse- no time picture. We argue that one should state, a priori, that this problem requires both pictures.

Continuity Equation Approach

The continuity equation ((2)) is part of the time picture (consistent with the work-kinetic picture). In classical physics, this viewpoint suffices, but it does not in quantum mechanics. We argue that the classical bias of only considering the time picture and not the impulse one is carried over in approaches which begin a priori with the continuity equation and do not a priori point out that an impulse picture is required as well.

As a result, these approaches seem to introduce the idea:

$$\text{density}(x,t) = W^*(x,t)W(x,t) \quad ((7))$$

(These approaches also consider the idea of irrotational flow which is a physical idea, but not the impulse one.)

The justification seems to be that such an approach yields the Schrodinger equation. We argue, however, that there should be a physical reason for using ((7)), just as there is for the continuity equation ((2)). We suggest that the impulse picture governs quantum interactions and is associated with the probability $\exp(ipx)$ for a free particle with momentum p. We suggest that this picture, together with the usual time continuity equation one, should be presented a priori as both are present in the quantum solution of a bound particle. In fact, one cannot dispense of the impulse picture because it describes interactions quantum mechanically. In the one dimensional photon reflection-refraction problem, it is actually the time energy picture which may be dispensed of (to a certain degree) if one is only interested in calculating B,C in terms of A. AA,BB,CC are fluxes, however, so even in this case the idea of time flow is present. Thus it is a dichotomy of the time-work and impulse-no time pictures which is needed.

Conclusion

In classical mechanics there exists a dichotomy of a time-velocity-kinetic energy picture associated with work and potential energy and a no time picture associated with impulses and changes in momentum. $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ have different velocities, but the same impulse. Traditionally, classical mechanics seems to bypass the impulse picture, focusing solely on the

time viewpoint i.e. conservation of energy or the equivalent Newton's second law form. This time viewpoint seems sufficient classically.

A problem with using only one viewpoint, however, appears in the one dimensional reflection-refraction of a photon. Photon count/energy conservation i.e. the time picture written in terms of fluxes AA, BB, CC for the incident, reflected and refracted beams yields only one equation: $AA/c = BB/c + CC/c_2$ where $c_2=c/n_2$. One is in fact forced to use the impulse picture to solve this problem i.e. bring BB/c to the LHS and use differences of squares: $A+B=C$ and $pA-pB=p_2C$ where $e=pc$. Thus both the time picture (AA is a flux) and the impulse picture must be used together. It is the impulse picture which governs the interactions and solves the problem (although the square root of flux is present which is associated with time), but the two impulse linked equations combine to give the single energy-time equation.

We suggest that in quantum mechanics, the impulse picture may not be dispensed of as is usually done in classical mechanics. When solving the bound state problem, $V(x)$, a potential, is often taken from classical mechanics. It is part of the energy-time viewpoint, but the impulse picture must also be included a priori. Impulse for a momentum p and its associated two dimensional probability $\exp(ipx)$ are used to determine p which cannot be discerned with certainty at a point x , but rather has probabilities within \hbar/p . As a result, an average of p 's and their $\exp(ipx)$ s is needed. This leads to an average $KE = \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \ \exp(ipx) \} / \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ \exp(ipx) \}$ such that $KE(x)+V(x) = E_n$.

The continuity equation ((2)) is also part of the time picture and ignores impulses which should be included a priori. As a result, approaches which derive the time-independent Schrodinger equation from the continuity equation introduce a math transform: $\text{density}(x,t) = W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$. We argue that $W(x,t)$ has physical meaning and is associated with the impulse picture i.e. for a bound state $W(x,t)=\exp(-iEt) \text{ Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$.

Thus in quantum mechanics a dichotomy of the time-energy-work picture and the no time-impulse picture must be utilized, we suggest.

References

1. Kaniadakis, G. Statistical Origins of Quantum Mechanics (2018)
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